

A Study on Socio Economic Status of Women Employees in Organized Retail Sector in Coimbatore City

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Abstract:- The Indian retail sector has opened vast employment opportunities and women employees are the preferred choice of retail to deal with sale for the certain product categories such as food and grocery, cosmetics, kids' products, jewellery, home decor and apparels etc. Young and smart women with an impressive communication ability are considered to be better employees as they manage to stay longer in the service industry as compared to men. This paper examines the profile, nature of jobs and the employment in retail outlets has influenced and improved the women employee's social status. How for the women employees in retail outlets has influenced and improved the people economic status?

Keywords:- Socio Status, Economic Status, Women Employees, Organized Retail.

I. INTRODUCTION

The retail industry employs more women than men - the ratio is 60:40 - and more women than men start their graduate careers in retail. Many women decide to stop at middle management when they have families, but there are still plenty who sit on retail operating boards. But the challenges facing women determined to make it as chief executives are greater than those encountered by men, both professionally and personally.

Effectively implementing employee retention program by increasing employee engagement ensures that the women employees are satisfied with their work, take pride in their work, report to duty on time, feel responsible for their job, feel valued for their contributions, and have high job satisfaction. As women employees actively focus on their work, it increases the productivity levels in the organization and leads to improvement in several associated areas. Employee engagement ensures that the women employees have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities in the organization. Increasing employee engagement helps to develop emotional connection, enthusiasm among the women employees that promotes teamwork and healthy environment at the workplace. Motivating women employees by offering them better opportunities for career development can help in

employee retention. Giving rewards, recognitions, promotions, and appreciation to employees can motivate them to increase their productivity, commitment to work, and loyalty to the organization. They feel that their contributions are valued in the organization. Giving incentives, pay hikes, bonuses can also help to motivate employees. Recognizing employee's contributions and aspirations motivates employee to work productively and increases his confidence that helps in employee retention. The top women have helped their companies grow and thrive in an unsettled retail environment, built and managed great teams, launched new strategic initiatives, mentored colleagues, and given back to the industry. The year 2018, will be the "Year of the Woman." Promoting team culture helps to actively involve all women employees in achieving the goals and in overall success of the organization.

Team building promotes team work and team effort that help employees to tackle work pressure and thus provide a competitive advantage to organization. Focusing on team building activities can help to reduce workplace conflicts between team members as they work in a team. Organizing team building games, seminars, outdoor events help to promote team spirit, unity, and reduce stress. Recognition of performance of women employees is an effective method of employee retention. Although monetary compensation can act as a motivating factor, openly recognizing the performance, initiative, and good work increases the morale and motivates the employee to work more productively. Appreciating the performance motivates the employee and they feel valuable within the organization. This helps in employee engagement and to increase the productivity levels.

➤ Objectives of the Study:

- To study the personal profile of the women employed in organized retail outlets in Coimbatore city.
- To assess the social and economic status of the women employed in organized retail outlets in Coimbatore city.
- To identify the problems faced by women employees.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. B.V. Sangvikar and Dr. Prafulla Pawar (2012) The study shows that some employees are interested in strategy formulation but they are not interested in promotional activities even though they showing interest in the word of mouth promotions, this kind of employee attitude found in various group of retail employees. The main of the study is to understand role of employee participation in marketing decisions of a retail organizations in India and to study extent of employee participation in various marketing decisions of a retail organization. The finding of this research shows that there are different groups of employee in retail organization on the basis of participation in marketing decisions.

Taruna Yadav and Sushma and Rani (2015) say in “Their study analyzed that the most important factor to influence and develop work-life balance is organization commitment as well as individual’s commitment. So they suggested that the organization should frame some HR strategies which will be helpful in creating stress free environment for working people which in turn will be helpful to improve the work life balance”.

Keene and Reynolds (2005) has done a study on work life balance of married employees in which they revealed that women were mostly affected by family demands so they are in the situation to make more work adjustments due to family demands than man.

Upadhyay and Gupta (2012) conclude that communication plays a major role in increasing the s satisfaction of an employee. Satisfied employees are reported to have high morale. Welfare measures and work experience does not necessarily relate to satisfaction.

➤ *Stress in Retail Sector:*

Retail employees have to balance the expectations of management and customers. Role-related stressors i.e. role conflicts and role ambiguities have been observed to add more strain to stressful internal environments (e.g., longer periods of higher performance expectations) by retail employees. Introduction Stress is defined as a permanent state of emotional turmoil that results in negative emotional, psycho-social and behavioral consequences, Studies on stress can help us further understand a possible way to reduce the negative effects of role introduction stressors and how retail employees can be better managed. Like any job, retail people will face stress. Those who do not learn to compile will suffer. Always on in the retail case - there’s a “go, go” mentality. It’s great at the store, but you can also find time for yourself. Retailers report significantly higher rates for mental health problems than any other profession, but this is not the case at all. While the psychological crisis seems to be relatively stable among the rest of the staff, it is getting worse for those who are retail. Emotional anxiety is not lightly sound.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodology is used in the study: (i) Study area: The study area is Coimbatore City (ii) Sampling Procedure: Convenient sampling method is followed (iii) Tools used: Percentage analysis, Chi-square analysis. (iv) Sources of data: Both primary and secondary data is used for the study.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table no 1: Table showing Distribution of Respondents by Perception on Standard of Living Standard of Living

Standard of Living	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Notably Improved	92	46.00
Improved	77	38.50
Indifferent	31	15.50

source: Primary Data

It found that perceptions on their standard of living. 46 percent of the respondents feel their standard of living has ‘notably improved’. 38 percent feel that their standard of living has ‘improved’ by employment. 15.50 percent of the respondents are indifferent about the issue. It is clear that most of the respondents agree that their standard of living has improved through employment.

Table no 2: Table showing Personal Profile of the employees working in retail stores

Particulars	Classification	Number of respondents	Percentage
Age group	15-25	25	12.5
	25 to 35	80	40
	35 to 50	75	37.5
	50 and above	20	10
Designation	Manager	18	9
	Supervisor	16	8
	Sales girls	75	37.5
	Cashier	43	21.5
	Senior sales associate	28	14
	Customer service	20	10
Marital status	Married	59	29.5
	Unmarried	119	59.5
	Divorced	18	9
	Single parent	11	5.5
Number of earning members	One	86	43
	Two	152	76
	Three and above	38	19
Monthly family income Less	5000-10000	57	28.5
	10000 -20000	119	59.5
	20000- to	24	12

than	30000		
Economic status	High	27	13.5
	Middle	78	39
	Low	95	47.5

It is found from the table no.2. the majority of respondent are belonged to age group less than 25; educational level being college level; designation as sales girls; married and belongs to nuclear family with two earning members Majority of the respondent’s monthly income is less than 10000; lives in rental house and belongs to below poverty level.

Table no 3 : Table showing the problems faced by the women respondents working in retail stores

Problems faced by retail employees	Classification	Number of respondents	Percentage
Added responsibilities & High work load	yes	112	56
	No	88	44
Coercion by supervisors	Yes	108	54
	No	92	46
Poor job security/ Job fear	Yes	69	34.5
	No	32	16
Less salary and benefits	yes	134	67
	No	66	33

Source: Primary data

It is found from the table no. 3, that majority of the women employees face problems like high work load, less salary, poor working conditions and poor job security.

Table no 4. Chi-square values-personal factors-social status of the respondents working in retail stores.

Personal factors	Chi-square value	Decision
Age	1.270	There is no association between Social status and age
Education level	3.476	There is association between Social status and educational level
Occupation	4.544	There is association between Social status and occupation
Number of earning members	0.287	There is association between Social status number of earning members
Monthly family income	0.232	There is association between Social status monthly family income

Source: Primary data; p value<=0.05

Hypothesis: Personal factors of the respondents have no significant influence on the economic status of the employees of retail stores.

V. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

- Retail employment has improved the social and economic status of the women employees. But this improvement is not to the expected level.
- women employees and also majority of them belong s to middle class family. Hence, it is proved that retail employment favour women employment which makes the country to develop both economic and socially improved. Hence, management should also provide good
- Majority of the women employees face problems like high work load, less salary, poor working conditions and less career development. Hence the management of retail stores should take necessary steps to make their employees happy by providing good workings, reasonable salary and work load.

VI. CONCLUSION

The value of having female employees in an organization is often cited. The majority of businesses nowadays are considered to find it difficult to retain their personnel. A significant element of handling the difficulty is finding, attracting, developing, and keeping the proper talent, and once it is discovered, there is a need for talent retention. Many variables influence workers and force them to change employment. Companies must manage a number of fancy strategies to retain personnel, and the reasons may be internal or external in nature. Although not every business can accommodate the needs of working parents, retailers can occasionally, especially have given that the internet makes it simpler to work from anywhere at any time. The respondents choose retail employment to support their family financially, convenient work timings, nearness to house, easy entry in to job, to support their education, to become an entrepreneur, parental/social pressure, free food and accommodation etc., Hence it concludes that, retail employment has contributed much to improve the social and economic development of the women employees.

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